

Multi-Robot Relative Localization and Formation Control Using Interior Angle Measurements

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Abstract—Inter-robot relative localization using accessible local measurements is crucial for various multi-robot missions in a GPS-denied environment. Due to its importance, it is meaningful to complement existing localization methods commonly based on distances or bearings between robots. Here, we propose a continuous relative localization approach using interior angle measurements for multi-robot systems in 2-D. Each robot measures those angles formed with neighboring robots. First, for a minimum three-robot case, we show that the inter-robot relative positions can be directly calculated from the robots' interior angles, the time derivative of interior angles, and inter-robot relative velocities, under the condition that the derivative of the interior angle intersected by the two neighboring robots is nonzero. To avoid this singularity case caused by a zero derivative of the interior angle at some instants, we propose a dynamical relative position estimator relying on the same three types of measurements. Using the estimated relative positions, a control law is designed to achieve a desired triangular formation specified by desired inter-robot relative positions. For the case where the system consists of more than three robots, the multi-robot relative localization is achieved in a directed and triangulated manner. The effects of measurement noise and robots' collinearity on the relative localization are also discussed. Finally, simulations and experiments are conducted to validate the proposed approach.

Index Terms—Relative localization, multi-robot system, formation control, estimation, multi-agent networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE roadmap for multi-robot systems aims to have autonomous agents making decisions based on mainly local information [34]. The relative position between mobile robots is an essential information to achieve fundamental tasks such as formation control and collision avoidance in order to exhibit higher-level behaviors [31]. Several types of sensors have been developed to, directly or indirectly, obtain robots' relative positions [23]. Direct measurement sensors include LiDAR,

The work of L. Chen was supported in part by the National Natural Science Foundation of China under Grant 62473190 and in part by Guangdong Provincial Natural Science Foundation under Grant 2024A1515011523 and in part by Guangdong Provincial Key Laboratory of Fully Actuated System Control Theory and Technology under Grant 2024B1212010002. The work of H.G. de Marina is supported by the grant Ramon y Cajal RYC2020-030090-I from the Spanish Ministry of Science, and the ERC Starting Grant *iSwarm* 101076091.

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stereo cameras, monocular cameras with prior knowledge of neighboring robots' dimensions, directional array of well-placed beacons with prior knowledge of their positions, and the combination of on-board distance and bearing sensors [13], [31]. When wireless communication is available, the indirect estimation of inter-robot relative positions, i.e., relative localization, has been studied recently by using distance or bearing information and some other auxiliary measurements [8], [12], [16], [25], [30]. For example, the relative localization based on distances between robots is studied in [2], [12], [16], [20], [25]. The relative localization algorithm in [15], [16] achieves the estimation of relative positions via distance-only measurements when neighboring agents perform linear-circular motions. The relative localization is also widely used for the coordination of multi-robot systems. An important application of relative localization in multi-robot systems is formation control [3], [12]. A persistently excited adaptive technique is proposed in [25] to achieve integrated relative localization and time-varying formations when the inter-robot distances and each robot's self-displacement are available. Different from distance measurements, bearing measurements are also widely used for relative localization [39]. The integrated relative localization and formation control using bearing-only measurements are studied in [35]. The integrated relative localization and circumnavigation of a moving target are achieved in [8] by using bearing measurements. Based on graph rigidity theory, relative localization using bearing measurements is investigated in [36].

Due to the significance of inter-robot relative position information in practical missions, it is meaningful to support and complement these existing localization methods commonly based on distances or bearings between robots [28]. With the same objective, we propose a multi-robot relative localization approach using robots' interior angle measurements. One of the reasons of using interior angles for relative localization is that the magnitude of each interior angle formed by any three robots is independent of the orientations of the robots' coordinate frames. Thus, interior angles can be measured by monocular cameras, and sensor arrays via angle of arrival and angle of departure modules [26], [29], without needing any North references or alignment of robots' coordinate frames. With this motivation, this work focuses on multi-robot relative localization using interior angle measurements. The three innovative aspects of this paper are summarized as follows:

a) Different from distance- and bearing-based localization, we provide a direct calculation approach for the determination of robots' relative positions using interior angles. In particular, we show the necessary and sufficient conditions of the direct

calculation approach.

b) Different from relative localization algorithms relying on North references and alignment of robots' frames, we propose a dynamical relative localization approach using angle measurements, which does not rely on North references and frames' alignment.

c) Instead of only achieving relative localization, integrated relative position estimator and formation control law are designed to make our relative position estimator compatible with displacement-based formation controllers.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces basic preliminaries and problem formulation. In Section III, we present the results about the relative localization and formation control for the three-robot case. The extension to multi-robot case is given in Section IV. Section V discusses the effects of measurement noises and collinearity. Simulations and experiments are provided in Section VI.

Notations: Consider a planar and mobile multi-robot system consisting of $N \geq 3$ robots. Label the robots from 1 to N and let $\mathcal{V} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ be the set of the robots. Denote robot i 's position by $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^2, i \in \mathcal{V}$ and let $p = [p_1^\top, p_2^\top, \dots, p_N^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{2N}$. Let $I_2, 1_N, \otimes, \lambda_{\max}, \lambda_{\min}, \det(\cdot)$ be the 2-by-2 identity matrix, N -by-1 column vector of all ones, the Kronecker product, the maximum eigenvalue, the minimum eigenvalue of a symmetric matrix, and the determinant of a square matrix, respectively. Denote by $R(\theta) := \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) \\ \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \in SO(2)$ the 2D rotation matrix with rotation angle $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$. Define \mathcal{N}_i as robot i 's neighbor set. Each robot conducts its measurements and executes its control commands under a static coordinate frame \sum_i . Define \sum_g as the global coordinate frame and let $R_g^i \in SO(2)$ be the rotation matrix describing the rotation from \sum_g to \sum_i . Define $p_i(t), p_j^i(t)$ as robot i 's time-varying position in \sum_g and \sum_j , respectively. For notation conciseness, whenever we describe a robot's variable with respect to \sum_g (resp. \sum_j), the superscript is omitted (resp. the superscript j is attached). The symbol of time variable ' t ' is also omitted in most places when no confusion is caused.

II. PRELIMINARIES AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, we first introduce some preliminaries, and then formulate the problem to be solved.

A. Interior angle measurements

For three non-coincident robots k, i, j , we define robot i 's interior angle measurement $\alpha_{kij} \in [0, 2\pi)$ with respect to robots k and j under the counterclockwise direction as [6]

$$\alpha_{kij} := \begin{cases} \arccos(b_{ij}^\top b_{ik}), & \text{if } b_{ij}^\top b_{ik} \geq 0, \\ 2\pi - \arccos(b_{ij}^\top b_{ik}), & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $b_{ij} := \frac{p_j - p_i}{\|p_j - p_i\|}$ with $l_{ij} := \|p_j - p_i\|$ is the bearing from robot i to robot j which is a unit vector, $i, j \in \mathcal{V}$, and $b_{ik}^\perp = R(\frac{\pi}{2})b_{ik} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} b_{ik}$ represents the unit vector obtained by rotating b_{ik} counterclockwise of $\frac{\pi}{2}$. Note that α_{kij} represents the angle rotating from the ray \overrightarrow{ik} to the ray \overrightarrow{ij} under the counterclockwise direction, which can be measured by robot

i 's onboard sensor, such as monocular camera or directional sensor arrays. The assumption that robot i can measure α_{kij} does imply that robot i can measure α_{jik} since $\alpha_{jik} \equiv 2\pi - \alpha_{kij}$.

Remark 1: The differences between bearings and angles lie in two aspects. An interior angle defined in (1) can be determined by the associated bearing vectors, but the bearing vectors cannot be directly derived from interior angles. The description of a robot's bearing measurements relies on the orientation of the robot's coordinate frame, while the description of angle measurements is independent of the orientation of the robot's coordinate frame since $b_{ij}^\top b_{ik}^i = b_{ij}^\top R_g^{i\top} R_g^i b_{ik} = b_{ij}^\top b_{ik}$. Thus, bearing measurements usually rely on the knowledge of Earth's magnetic north, while angle measurements do not.

Remark 2: There are mainly three types of sensors that can measure interior angles, namely cameras, sensor arrays, and lens-MIMO system. Cameras are usually subject to the constraints of limited field of view and light conditions [10]. Directional sensor arrays (such as the Bluetooth 5.1 technology-based devices [27]) and lens-MIMO systems [18] can also provide angle information by measuring the angle of arrival/departure of a signal.

B. Angle-induced linear equations in triangles

As shown in Fig. 1, we take three interior angles $\alpha_{kij}, \alpha_{ijk}, \alpha_{jki}$ from the non-degenerate triangle $\triangle ijk$ as an example to establish an angle-induced linear equation [7]. Rotating the unit vector b_{ik} with angle α_{kij} under counter-

Fig. 1. Establish angle-induced linear equation within $\triangle ijk$

clockwise direction yields

$$(p_j - p_i) / \|p_j - p_i\| = R(\alpha_{kij})(p_k - p_i) / \|p_k - p_i\|. \quad (2)$$

According to [7], using the law of sines $\frac{\|p_k - p_i\|}{\|p_j - p_i\|} = \frac{\sin \alpha_{ijk}}{\sin \alpha_{jki}}$ and the fact (2), the angle-induced linear equation within $\triangle ijk$ can be written as

$$\sin \alpha_{jki}(p_i - p_k) - \sin \alpha_{ijk} R^\top(\alpha_{kij})(p_i - p_j) = 0, \quad (3)$$

where the coefficient matrices are only related to the interior angles $\alpha_{jki}, \alpha_{ijk}, \alpha_{kij}$. For a degenerate triangle $\triangle ijk$, i.e., p_i, p_j, p_k are collinear, the angle-induced linear equation (3) degrades into a trivial equation $0 = 0$. It is also worth mentioning that an interior angle defined in (1) is highly nonlinear with respect to the robots' positions p_i, p_j, p_k . However, the angle-induced linear equation (3) decouples this nonlinearity by establishing the linear relationship between the relative positions $p_i - p_k, p_i - p_j$ and $\sin \alpha_{ijk}, \sin \alpha_{jki}, \cos \alpha_{ijk}, \cos \alpha_{jki}$. This

relationship will become the foundation to calculate/estimate $p_i - p_k, p_i - p_j$ from $\alpha_{jki}, \alpha_{kij}, \alpha_{ijk}$.

Assumption 1: Each robot has at least two neighbors. The communication topology is derived from measurement topology, of which both are triangular.

The above assumption ensures that each robot can participate in a triangular formation with two neighboring robots, ensuring triangles as the basic units for relative position estimation and formation control.

Remark 3: Due to the fact $R(\alpha_{ijk})R(\theta) \equiv R(\theta)R(\alpha_{ijk})$, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$, one has from (3) that $\sin \alpha_{jki}R(\theta)(p_i - p_k) - \sin \alpha_{ijk}R^\top(\alpha_{kij})R(\theta)(p_i - p_j) = 0$ holds for $\forall \theta \in \mathbb{R}$.

C. Problem formulation

In this paper, we are interested in recovering/estimating inter-robot relative position $p_{ij} := p_j - p_i$ from three types of locally available measurements, which are angle measurements α_{jik} , derivative of angle measurements $\dot{\alpha}_{jik}$, and relative velocity $\dot{p}_{ij}, \dot{p}_{ik}$ with respect to the neighbors $j, k \in \mathcal{N}_i$. Simultaneously, we are also interested in using the estimated relative positions to achieve a desired multi-robot formation. These two objectives can be mathematically described by

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{p}_{eij}(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} (\hat{p}_{ij}(t) - (p_j(t) - p_i(t))) = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{p}_{fij}(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} (p_{ij}(t) - (p_j^*(t) - p_i^*(t))) = 0, \quad (5)$$

where $\tilde{p}_{eij}(t) = \hat{p}_{ij}(t) - p_{ij}(t)$ and $\tilde{p}_{fij}(t) = p_{ij}(t) - p_{ij}^*(t)$, $i, j \in \mathcal{V}, j \in \mathcal{N}_i$, are defined as the estimation error and formation tracking error, respectively, and $\hat{p}_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denotes the estimate of p_{ij} , and $p_{ij}^* \in \mathbb{R}^2$ represents the desired relative position of robot j with respect to robot i . To achieve these objectives, we first make some assumptions and problem statements.

Assumption 2: Each robot can measure interior angles and derivatives of interior angles with respect to its neighbors.

In this paper, if each robot shares a common coordinate frame with the other robots to measure relative velocities, then we aim to achieve (4)-(5) in this common coordinate frame. If each robot $i, i \in \mathcal{V}$ uses its own local coordinate frame \sum_i to measure relative velocities, then we aim to achieve (4)-(5) in \sum_i correspondingly.

Remark 4: For the continuous relative localization using distance measurements in [12] and bearing-based formation control in [37], the derivatives of distance and bearing measurements are used, respectively. Similarly, in this continuous relative localization based on angle measurements, the derivatives of angle measurements are needed. In addition, the relative localization for mobile multi-robot systems is different from the localization problem of wireless sensor networks where the nodes are stationary and anchor nodes (whose *absolute* positions are known) always exist [22].

III. RELATIVE LOCALIZATION AND FORMATION CONTROL FOR 3-ROBOT CASE

We begin by examining relative localization in the simplest multi-robot system configuration, namely three robots labeled

by 1, 2, and 3. The three robots form a triangle, denoted as $\triangle 123$. For notation conciseness, we first discuss the case that all variables are described in \sum_g (i.e., the robots share a common coordinate frame), then discuss the case that they are described in each robot's local coordinate frame.

A. Direct calculation of inter-robot relative position

For a dynamic triangle $\triangle 123$ formed by time-varying $p_1(t), p_2(t)$ and $p_3(t)$, according to (3), one has

$$\sin \alpha_{231}(p_1 - p_3) - \sin \alpha_{123}R^\top(\alpha_{312})(p_1 - p_2) = 0 \quad (6)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \sin \alpha_{123}(p_3 - p_2) - \sin \alpha_{312}R^\top(\alpha_{231})(p_3 - p_1) \\ &= \sin \alpha_{123}(p_3 - p_1 + p_1 - p_2) - \sin \alpha_{312}R^\top(\alpha_{231})(p_3 - p_1) \\ &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Writing (6)-(7) into a compact form yields

$$M_1^{\triangle 123}(\alpha)[p_{21}^\top, p_{31}^\top]^\top = 0, \quad (8)$$

where $M_1^{\triangle 123}(\alpha) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$ and

$$M_1^{\triangle 123}(\alpha) = \begin{bmatrix} -\sin \alpha_{123}R^\top(\alpha_{312}) & \sin \alpha_{231}I_2 \\ \sin \alpha_{123}I_2 & \sin \alpha_{312}R^\top(\alpha_{231}) - \sin \alpha_{123}I_2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Lemma 1: For an arbitrary non-degenerate $\triangle 123$, $\text{Rank}(M_1^{\triangle 123}(\alpha)) = 2$, i.e., (6) and (7) are always linearly dependent/interchangeable. \square

Proof 1: Since the rotation matrix $R^\top(\alpha_{312})$ is always nonsingular, one has $\text{Rank}(M_1^{\triangle 123}(\alpha)) \geq 2$ for any non-degenerate triangle. In addition, according to Remark 3, it can be obtained that both $[p_{21}^\top, p_{31}^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^4$ and $\begin{bmatrix} R(\pi/2)p_{21} \\ R(\pi/2)p_{31} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^4$ lie in the null space of $M_1^{\triangle 123}(\alpha)$. Since these two vectors are linearly independent, one has $\text{Rank}(M_1^{\triangle 123}(\alpha)) \leq 2$. Thus, one has $\text{Rank}(M_1^{\triangle 123}(\alpha)) = 2$.

As given in Lemma 1, the triangle $\triangle 123$ needs to be non-degenerate, for which we further make the following assumption.

Assumption 3: There are no inter-robot collision and collinearity in $\triangle 123$, or equivalently, $\alpha_{jik}, \dot{\alpha}_{jik}, j, i, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ are well-defined and continuous.

Remark 5: When a collinearity occurs among the three robots, two of the three interior angles in the triangle will change from 0^+ to $2\pi^-$ or from $2\pi^-$ to 0^+ , which makes these two interior angles discontinuous. Therefore, Assumption 3 requires that there should not exist collinearity among the robots. In practice, robots are usually equipped with on-board sensors for collision avoidance, such as ultrasound. Collinearity issue will be discussed further in a later subsection.

Then, taking the time-derivative of (6) and (7) yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \dot{\alpha}_{231} \cos \alpha_{231} p_{31} + \sin \alpha_{231} \dot{p}_{31} - \sin \alpha_{123} R^\top(\alpha_{312}) \dot{p}_{21} \\ & - \dot{\alpha}_{123} \cos \alpha_{123} R^\top(\alpha_{312}) p_{21} - \dot{\alpha}_{312} \sin \alpha_{123} R^\top(\alpha_{312} + \frac{\pi}{2}) p_{21} \\ & = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \dot{\alpha}_{123} \cos \alpha_{123} (p_3 - p_1 + p_1 - p_2) + \sin \alpha_{123} \dot{p}_{23} \\ & - \sin \alpha_{312} R^\top(\alpha_{231}) \dot{p}_{13} - \dot{\alpha}_{312} \cos \alpha_{312} R^\top(\alpha_{231}) p_{13} \\ & - \dot{\alpha}_{231} \sin \alpha_{312} R^\top(\alpha_{231} + \pi/2) p_{13} = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

respectively. After algebraic manipulation, from the equations (9)-(10) we can arrive at

$$M_2^{\Delta 123} \begin{bmatrix} p_{13} \\ p_{21} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \alpha_{123} R^\top(\alpha_{312}) \dot{p}_{21} - \sin \alpha_{231} \dot{p}_{31} \\ \sin \alpha_{312} R^\top(\alpha_{231}) \dot{p}_{13} - \sin \alpha_{123} \dot{p}_{23} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

where $M_2^{\Delta 123} = \begin{bmatrix} -\dot{\alpha}_{231} \cos \alpha_{231} I_2 & M_2^{(12)} \\ M_2^{(21)} & \dot{\alpha}_{123} \cos \alpha_{123} I_2 \end{bmatrix}$, $M_2^{(12)} = -\dot{\alpha}_{123} \cos \alpha_{123} R^\top(\alpha_{312}) - \dot{\alpha}_{312} \sin \alpha_{123} R^\top(\alpha_{312} + \frac{\pi}{2})$, $M_2^{(21)} = \dot{\alpha}_{123} \cos \alpha_{123} I_2 - \dot{\alpha}_{312} \cos \alpha_{312} R^\top(\alpha_{231}) - \dot{\alpha}_{231} \sin \alpha_{312} R^\top(\alpha_{231} + \pi/2)$. We remind the readers that $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ depends on those angles α and derivative of angles $\dot{\alpha}$ that are within $\Delta 123$. Note that in $\Delta 123$, one always has $\dot{\alpha}_{123} + \dot{\alpha}_{231} + \dot{\alpha}_{312} = 0$, $p_{13} + p_{21} + p_{32} = 0$, $\dot{p}_{13} + \dot{p}_{21} + \dot{p}_{32} = 0$, and

$$\alpha_{123} + \alpha_{231} + \alpha_{312} = \begin{cases} \pi, & \text{if } 0 < \alpha_{123} < \pi, \\ 5\pi, & \text{if } \pi < \alpha_{123} < 2\pi, \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Thus, both the vectors in the right side of (11) and the matrix $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ are only related with the available sensing information of relative velocities $\dot{p}_1 - \dot{p}_2, \dot{p}_3 - \dot{p}_1$, interior angles $\alpha_{123}, \alpha_{231}$, and the derivatives of interior angles $\dot{\alpha}_{123}, \dot{\alpha}_{231}$. Moreover, the equality (11) indicates that if the matrix $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ is invertible, then the relative positions p_{13}, p_{21} can be directly calculated/obtained without using any dynamical estimators. However, it can be easily seen that if $\Delta 123$'s motion is the combination of translation, rotation and scaling, then $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ becomes not invertible because $\dot{\alpha}_{jik} = 0, \forall i, j, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $M_2^{\Delta 123} = 0$.

Remark 6: In practical context, although the original two angle-induced linear constraints (6) and (7) can be linearly dependent, the time-derivatives of them (9) and (10) can be linearly independent. This is because (9) and (10) also additionally associate with robots' relative velocities and derivatives of interior angles, which makes the direct calculation of relative positions from (11) possible. In addition, since both (9) and (10) are related with p_{13}, p_{21} , one cannot calculate one of the relative positions p_{13}, p_{21} separately, but calculate two relative positions simultaneously.

Now, we discuss when the matrix $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ is invertible such that relative position can be directly calculated.

Proposition 1: Under Assumption 3, one has that

- (a) $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ is invertible if and only if $\dot{\alpha}_{312} \neq 0$;
- (b) $\text{Rank}(M_2^{\Delta 123}) = 2$ if and only if $\dot{\alpha}_{312} = 0$ and $\dot{\alpha}_{123} = -\dot{\alpha}_{231} \neq 0$;
- (c) $\text{Rank}(M_2^{\Delta 123}) = 0$ if and only if $\dot{\alpha}_{312} = \dot{\alpha}_{123} = \dot{\alpha}_{231} = 0$;
- (d) if $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ is invertible, then the relative position can be directly calculated from (11) by

$$\begin{bmatrix} p_{13} \\ p_{21} \end{bmatrix} = (M_2^{\Delta 123})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \sin \alpha_{123} R^\top(\alpha_{312}) \dot{p}_{21} - \sin \alpha_{231} \dot{p}_{31} \\ \sin \alpha_{312} R^\top(\alpha_{231}) \dot{p}_{13} - \sin \alpha_{123} \dot{p}_{23} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

□

The proof of Proposition 1 is given in Appendix A. From Proposition 1.(a), one has that $\dot{\alpha}_{312} \neq 0$ is the necessary and sufficient to ensure that there exists a unique solution $[p_{13}^\top, p_{21}^\top]^\top$ in (11). Although this proposition is intuitive from an observability point of view, its proof is not straightforward since the triangle is dynamical.

According to Proposition 1, the direct calculation of relative positions becomes invalid once $\dot{\alpha}_{312} = 0$ or $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ is singular. Therefore, we aim to propose a dynamical estimation approach in the next subsection. Before presenting the dynamical estimation approach, we discuss the case that robot 1 uses its own local coordinate frame to conduct the relative position calculation (13).

Lemma 2: When robot $i, i = 1, 2, 3$ uses its own local coordinate frame \sum_i to conduct the sensor measurements, then the relative position calculation in (13) becomes

$$\begin{bmatrix} p_{13}^i \\ p_{21}^i \end{bmatrix} = (M_2^{\Delta 123})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \sin \alpha_{123} R_i^\top(\alpha_{312}) \dot{p}_{21}^i - \sin \alpha_{231} \dot{p}_{31}^i \\ \sin \alpha_{312} R_i^\top(\alpha_{231}) \dot{p}_{13}^i - \sin \alpha_{123} \dot{p}_{23}^i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

where p_{1j}^i and $\dot{p}_{1j}^i, j = 2, 3$ represent the relative position and relative velocity described in \sum_i , respectively. □

Proof 2: When all the variables are described in robot 1's local coordinate frame, the left side of (11) becomes $M_2^{\Delta 123} \begin{bmatrix} R_i^g p_{13}^i \\ R_i^g p_{21}^i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_i^g 0 \\ 0 R_i^g \end{bmatrix} M_2^{\Delta 123} \begin{bmatrix} p_{13}^i \\ p_{21}^i \end{bmatrix}$ where we have used the facts introduced in Remarks 1-3. The right side of (11), with abbreviated notations ($S_1 = \sin \alpha_{312}, S_2 = \sin \alpha_{123}, S_3 = \sin \alpha_{231}, \alpha_1 = \alpha_{312}, \alpha_2 = \alpha_{123}, \alpha_3 = \alpha_{231}$), becomes $\begin{bmatrix} S_2 R_i^\top(\alpha_1) R_i^g \dot{p}_{21}^i - S_3 R_i^g \dot{p}_{31}^i \\ S_1 R_i^\top(\alpha_3) R_i^g \dot{p}_{13}^i - S_2 R_i^g \dot{p}_{23}^i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_i^g 0 \\ 0 R_i^g \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} S_2 R_i^\top(\alpha_1) \dot{p}_{21}^i - S_3 \dot{p}_{31}^i \\ S_1 R_i^\top(\alpha_3) \dot{p}_{13}^i - S_2 \dot{p}_{23}^i \end{bmatrix}$. Substituting the above facts into (11) yields (14), which implies that if the relative velocities are measured in \sum_i , then the relative positions calculated by (11) are also in \sum_i .

Remark 7: In (14), for conciseness, we only provide the determination of relative positions p_{13}^i and p_{21}^i . It is worth mentioning that $p_{23}^i = p_{21}^i + p_{13}^i$, which indicates that the relative position p_{23}^i can be obtained from p_{21}^i and p_{13}^i . In other words, for triangle Δijk , given arbitrary two inter-agent relative positions p_{ij}, p_{jk} , the remaining one inter-agent relative position p_{ik} can be uniquely determined.

Remark 8: For conciseness, the linear equation (2) takes p_i as the intersecting point since we only take robot i as an example to derive results for triangle Δijk . The results can be extended to robot j by replacing number i with j , j with k , and k with i , respectively. From Proposition 1, for the relative localization of p_{ij} and $p_{ik}, i, j, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, the angle α_{jik} intersected by p_{ij} and p_{ik} should be time-varying.

B. Dynamical estimation of inter-robot relative position

Let $\hat{p}_{13} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\hat{p}_{21} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ be the estimations of p_{13} and p_{21} , respectively. The aim of this subsection is to design dynamical estimators $\hat{p}_{13}, \hat{p}_{21}$ using the same three types of sensor measurements introduced in Section II.C such that $\hat{p}_{13}(t) \rightarrow p_{13}(t)$ and $\hat{p}_{21}(t) \rightarrow p_{21}(t)$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

Towards this end, we design the dynamical relative position estimator as

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{p}}_{13} \\ \dot{\hat{p}}_{21} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_{13} \\ \dot{p}_{21} \end{bmatrix} - k_c \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_{13} \\ \hat{p}_{21} \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ k_c \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right)^\top \begin{bmatrix} \sin \alpha_{123} R^\top(\alpha_{312}) \dot{p}_{21} - \sin \alpha_{231} \dot{p}_{31} \\ \sin \alpha_{312} R^\top(\alpha_{231}) \dot{p}_{13} - \sin \alpha_{123} \dot{p}_{23} \end{bmatrix}, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where k_c is a positive scalar used to tune the convergence speed, and $\dot{p}_{23} = \dot{p}_{21} + \dot{p}_{13}$. It is worth mentioning that different from (13), the inverse on $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ is not needed in (15). It can be easily seen that only the information of relative velocities, interior angles, and derivatives of interior angles is required in the designed estimator (15). Note that the dynamical relative position estimator (15) can be executed in arbitrary one of the robots 1,2 and 3 given the needed measurement information. Now, we present the main results.

Theorem 1: Under the estimator (15) and Assumptions 2 and 3, the estimation errors $\tilde{p}_{e13}(t)$ and $\tilde{p}_{e21}(t)$ globally and exponentially converge to zero if and only if there exist positive scalars γ_1, γ_2, T_1 such that $\forall t > 0$,

$$\gamma_1 I_4 \leq \int_t^{t+T_1} \left(M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) d\tau \leq \gamma_2 I_4. \quad (16)$$

Moreover, if $\exists \tau_0 \in [t, t+T_1]$ for $\forall t > 0$ such that $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(\tau_0) \neq 0$ and $\forall \tau \in [t, t+T_1], \forall t > 0$, $|\dot{\alpha}_{ijk}(\tau)|, i, j, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ are bounded, then (16) holds. \square

The proof of Theorem 1 is given in Appendix B. We provide two insights for this result. Firstly, using $\left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}$ in the dynamical relative position estimator (15) is to construct the globally and asymptotically estimation dynamics (39), which is inspired by the design of the classical least-square estimator. Secondly, (16) is a persistent excitation condition relating to the robots' interior angles, which is different from the corresponding one in distance-based relative localization that is related to robots' relative velocities [12]. Persistent excitation conditions are commonly required in other relative localization or formation control problems [12], [25], [32]. According to Theorem 1, if inter-robot relative positions $p_{12}(t), p_{13}(t)$ or interior angles are kept as constants, the condition (16) does not hold, in which the estimation errors will not converge. Intuitively, the sufficient condition provided in Theorem 1 implies that within each time period $[t, t+T_1]$, $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t)$ should not always be zero (corresponding to the existence of lower bound of (16)), and $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t), \dot{\alpha}_{123}(t), \dot{\alpha}_{231}(t)$ should be upper bounded (corresponding to the existence of upper bound of (16)). Obviously, this condition is lighter and can be satisfied more easily than the condition required in Proposition 1, i.e., $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t) \neq 0$ for all time instants. Also note that the estimator (15) needs more computations and iterations than the direct approach (13).

In addition, under Assumptions 2 and 3, it becomes straightforward from Lemma 2 that if robot $i, i = 1, 2, 3$ has its own local coordinate frame \sum_i to conduct the sensor measurements $\hat{p}_{ij}^i, j \in \mathcal{N}_i$, then under (15) the estimated positions $[\hat{p}_{13}^\top, \hat{p}_{21}^\top]^\top$ globally and exponentially converge to $[p_{13}^i, p_{21}^i]^\top$ if and only if the condition (16) holds.

C. Simultaneous relative localization and formation with aligned coordinate frames

After having the estimated relative positions, we now investigate the usage of them for multi-robot formation control. We consider the scenario that robot 1 is the leader robot whose velocity is $\dot{p}_1(t) \in \mathbb{R}^2$, while robots 2 and 3 are follower robots which are governed by

$$\dot{p}_i(t) = u_i(t), i = 2, 3, \quad (17)$$

where $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the position and $u_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the control input of robot i . Then, the aim of simultaneous relative localization and formation in this 3-robot case can be specified into designing $u_2(t), u_3(t)$ such that $\hat{p}_{21}(t) \rightarrow p_{21}^*(t)$ and $\hat{p}_{31}(t) \rightarrow p_{31}^*(t)$. Due to the relations $p_{21}^*(t) - p_{31}^*(t) \equiv p_{23}^*(t)$ and $p_{21}(t) - p_{31}(t) \equiv p_{23}(t)$, we define the formation in a directed manner, meaning that the control inputs are designed to regulate $p_{21}(t)$ and $p_{31}(t)$, while $p_{23}(t)$ evolves passively as a consequence of these regulations. It is worth mentioning that the nonholonomic dynamics of unicycle robots can also be transferred to the first-order model (17) by shifting the robot's controlling point with a finite distance from the actual center of the robot [38]. In practical applications, the controlling point is typically located within the robot's horizontal area. As a result, the distance between two robots' controlling points is always greater than zero, directly satisfying the no inter-robot collision condition in Assumption 3.

Towards this end, we design the simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws as

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{p}}_{13} \\ \dot{\hat{p}}_{12} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_{13} \\ \dot{p}_{12} \end{bmatrix} - k_c \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_{13} \\ \hat{p}_{12} \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ k_c \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right)^\top \begin{bmatrix} \sin \alpha_{123} R^\top(\alpha_{312}) \dot{p}_{21} - \sin \alpha_{231} \dot{p}_{31} \\ \sin \alpha_{312} R^\top(\alpha_{231}) \dot{p}_{13} - \sin \alpha_{123} \dot{p}_{23} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$- k_p \begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_{13} - p_{13}^* \\ \hat{p}_{12} - p_{12}^* \end{bmatrix},$$

$$u_2 = \dot{p}_1 + \dot{p}_{12}^* - k_p (\hat{p}_{12} - p_{12}^*), \quad (19)$$

$$u_3 = \dot{p}_1 + \dot{p}_{13}^* - k_p (\hat{p}_{13} - p_{13}^*), \quad (20)$$

where k_p is a positive scalar, and $\dot{p}_{13}, \dot{p}_{12}$ are executed in robots 3 and 2, respectively. It is worth noting that when the relative position estimator (15) is used for the formation control, a new term $-k_p \begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_{13}(t) - p_{13}^*(t) \\ \hat{p}_{12}(t) - p_{12}^*(t) \end{bmatrix}$ is added in (18), whose effect will be introduced later. For the formation control laws (19)-(20), the feedforward term $\dot{p}_1(t) + \dot{p}_{1i}^*(t), i = 2, 3$ is needed due to the time-varying $p_1(t)$ and $p_{1i}^*(t)$. Since the robots have aligned coordinate frames in this case, robots 2 and 3 can know $\dot{p}_1(t)$ via robot 1's onboard self-velocity measurement, together with the available communication between robot 1 and robots 2, 3, while $\dot{p}_{1i}^*(t)$ is naturally required when the desired formation is time-varying [9]. To avoid delay, the inter-robot communication can be achieved by, for example, high-speed 5G communication technology. Except for the feedforward term $\dot{p}_1(t) + \dot{p}_{1i}^*(t)$, the simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws (18)-(20) only need the information of relative velocities, interior angles, and derivatives of interior angles. Before presenting the results, we introduce an assumption on the desired relative positions.

Assumption 4: (a) The desired relative positions $p_{ij}^*(t)$, $i, j \in \mathcal{V}$, $i \neq j$ are all continuously differentiable, nonzero, and their first time-derivatives $\dot{p}_{ij}^*(t)$ are bounded. (b) In addition, to avoid the desired formation to be collinear among neighboring robots $i, j, k \in \mathcal{V}$, we assume $p_{ij}^*(t) \neq \kappa p_{jk}^*(t)$, $\forall \kappa \in \mathbb{R}_{\neq 0}$.

Note that Assumption 4 is on the desired relative positions, but not on the actual relative positions, and hence different from Assumption 3.

Then, one has the following results.

Theorem 2: Under the simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws (18)-(20) and Assumptions 2, 3 and 4, the estimation errors $\tilde{p}_{e1i}(t)$ and the formation errors $\tilde{p}_{f1i}(t)$, $i = 2, 3$ globally and exponentially converge to zero if and only if there exist positive scalars γ_3, γ_4, T_2 such that $\forall t > 0$,

$$\gamma_3 I_8 \leq \int_t^{t+T_2} \left[k_c (M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau))^{\top} M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) + k_p I_4 \quad k_p I_4 \right] d\tau \leq \gamma_4 I_8. \quad (21)$$

Moreover, if $\exists \tau_0 \in [t, t+T_2]$ for $\forall t > 0$ such that $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(\tau_0) \neq 0$, then the condition (21) always holds under the simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws (18)-(20). \square

The proof of Theorem 2 is given in Appendix C. One can see from the proof of Theorem 2 that the term $-k_p \begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_{13}(t) - p_{13}^*(t) \\ \hat{p}_{12}(t) - p_{12}^*(t) \end{bmatrix}$ in the estimator (18) makes the system matrix of the closed-loop dynamics of (18) symmetric, without which the stability analysis will become more challenging.

Note that the sufficient condition for (21) in Theorem 2 only requires the existence of lower bound in (21), i.e., within each time period $[t, t+T_2]$, $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t)$ should not always be zero, which is different with the sufficient condition for (16) in Theorem 1. According to Theorem 2, if the desired formation or interior angles is stationary, i.e., $\dot{p}_{ij}^* = 0$, then the condition (21) does not hold. In other words, the convergence of $\tilde{p}_{e1i}(t)$ and $\tilde{p}_{f1i}(t)$ under (18)-(20) is achieved only when the desired formation is time-varying. Now, we discuss the possible design method such that $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t)$ will not always be zero. First, we note that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d \cos \alpha_{312}}{dt} &= (-\sin \alpha_{312}) \dot{\alpha}_{312} = \dot{b}_{13}^{\top} b_{12} + b_{13}^{\top} \dot{b}_{12} \quad (22) \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{P_{b_{13}}}{\|p_1 - p_3\|} (\dot{p}_3 - \dot{p}_1) \right)^{\top} b_{12} + b_{13}^{\top} \frac{P_{b_{12}}}{\|p_1 - p_2\|} (\dot{p}_2 - \dot{p}_1) \right], \end{aligned}$$

where $P_{b_{ij}} = I_2 - b_{ij} b_{ij}^{\top}$. Therefore, substituting (19)-(20) into (22) yields

$$\begin{aligned} (-\sin \alpha_{312}) \dot{\alpha}_{312} &= \left[\left(\frac{P_{b_{13}}}{\|p_1 - p_3\|} (\dot{p}_{13}^* - k_p p_{e13} - k_p p_{f13}) \right)^{\top} b_{12} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + b_{13}^{\top} \frac{P_{b_{12}}}{\|p_1 - p_2\|} (\dot{p}_{12}^* - k_p p_{e12} - k_p p_{f12}) \right]. \quad (23) \end{aligned}$$

According to Assumption 3, $\sin \alpha_{312}(t) \neq 0$. Therefore, when the robots have not reached the desired formation, $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t)$ has a high probability to be nonzero, under which the lower bound of (21) exists. However, when the robots have converged to the desired formation, one has $p_{e1i}(t) \rightarrow 0$, $p_{f1i}(t) \rightarrow 0$, $i = 2, 3$, under which we can design $\dot{p}_{13}^*(t)$, $\dot{p}_{12}^*(t)$ in (23) such that

$\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t) \neq 0$. Therefore, one can design the desired time-varying formation using the following strategy such that the sufficient condition in Theorem 1 can be satisfied in a high probability: properly select $T_2 > 0$ and $p_{12}^*(t)$, $p_{13}^*(t)$ such that $\forall t > 0, \exists \tau_0 \in [t, t+T_2]$, $\frac{\dot{p}_{13}^*(\tau_0)(I_2 - b_{13}^*(\tau_0) b_{13}^{\top}(\tau_0))}{\|p_{13}^*(\tau_0)\|} b_{12}(\tau_0) + b_{13}^{\top}(\tau_0) \frac{(I_2 - b_{12}^*(\tau_0) b_{12}^{\top}(\tau_0))}{\|p_{12}^*(\tau_0)\|} p_{12}^*(\tau_0) \neq 0$, where $b_{1i}^* = p_{1i}^*/\|p_{1i}^*\|$, $i = 2, 3$. This strategy in general aims to avoid $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t) \equiv 0$. Note that for static desired formations or dynamical desired formations with translational, rotational and scaling motions, the angle α_{312}^* will be constant, under which the persistent excitation condition (21) does not hold and the convergence is not guaranteed. Even for this case when the condition (21) does not hold, we remark that the formation errors are always bounded by the initial formation errors and estimation errors. This is because the time-derivative of the Lyapunov function $V_1(t)$ designed in (52) is always negative semi-definite. Then, it follows that $\|\tilde{p}_{f1i}(t)\| \leq \|\tilde{p}_{f1i}(t)\| \leq V_1(t) \leq V_1(0) = 0.5[\tilde{p}_{e1}^{\top}(0) \tilde{p}_{f1}^{\top}(0)] \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{p}_{e1}(0) \\ \tilde{p}_{f1}(0) \end{bmatrix}$ where $i = 2, 3$. Therefore, if the initial formation errors and estimation errors are small, the proposed control strategy (18)-(20) can guarantee the formation tracking errors to be small for any feasible desired formations, even for the situation that the desired interior angles keep constant.

D. Simultaneous relative localization and formation without aligned coordinate frames

Now, we consider the case that robots 2 and 3 have their own local coordinate frames. The fact $p_{ij}^i \neq -p_{ji}^j$ makes the simultaneous relative location and formation task quite challenging and different from the case in last section.

We denote the estimation of p_{13}, p_{12} in robots 2 and 3 as $\hat{p}_{13}^2, \hat{p}_{12}^2$ and $\hat{p}_{13}^3, \hat{p}_{12}^3$, respectively. In this section, we assume that robot 1 will move to its desired constant position $p_1^* \in \mathbb{R}^2$ by using the control law $\dot{p}_1^* = u_1^* = -(p_1 - p_1^*)$. Then, we design the simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws as

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{p}}_{13}^2 \\ \dot{\hat{p}}_{12}^2 \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_{13}^2 \\ \dot{p}_{12}^2 \end{bmatrix} - k_c \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right)^{\top} M_2^{\Delta 123} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_{13}^2 \\ \hat{p}_{12}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (24) \\ &\quad + k_c \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right)^{\top} \begin{bmatrix} \sin \alpha_{123} R^{\top}(\alpha_{312}) \hat{p}_{21}^2 - \sin \alpha_{231} \hat{p}_{31}^2 \\ \sin \alpha_{312} R^{\top}(\alpha_{231}) \hat{p}_{31}^2 - \sin \alpha_{123} \hat{p}_{32}^2 \end{bmatrix} \\ &\quad - k_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \hat{p}_{12}^2 - p_{12}^{*2} \end{bmatrix}, \\ u_2^* &= \dot{p}_2^* = \dot{p}_{12}^{*2} - k_p (\hat{p}_{12}^2 - p_{12}^{*2}), \quad (25) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{p}}_{13}^3 \\ \dot{\hat{p}}_{12}^3 \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_{13}^3 \\ \dot{p}_{12}^3 \end{bmatrix} - k_c \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right)^{\top} M_2^{\Delta 123} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_{13}^3 \\ \hat{p}_{12}^3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (26) \\ &\quad + k_c \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right)^{\top} \begin{bmatrix} \sin \alpha_{123} R^{\top}(\alpha_{312}) \hat{p}_{21}^3 - \sin \alpha_{231} \hat{p}_{31}^3 \\ \sin \alpha_{312} R^{\top}(\alpha_{231}) \hat{p}_{31}^3 - \sin \alpha_{123} \hat{p}_{32}^3 \end{bmatrix} \\ &\quad - k_p \begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_{13}^3 - p_{13}^{*3} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\ u_3^* &= \dot{p}_3^* = \dot{p}_{13}^{*3} - k_p (\hat{p}_{13}^3 - p_{13}^{*3}), \quad (27) \end{aligned}$$

where (24)-(25) are executed in robot 2's local coordinate frame, (26)-(27) are executed in robot 3's local coordinate

frame, and p_{12}^{*2} (resp. p_{13}^{*3}) is the desired relative position of robot 2 (resp. robot 3) with respect to robot 1 described in robot 2's (resp. robot 3's) local coordinate frame. Note that to execute (24)-(25), robot 2 also only needs to measure the interior angles, derivative of angles and relative velocities in its local coordinate frame, where the relative velocities in the robot's local coordinate frame can be measured by radar or other sensors based on Doppler effect [24]. Compared to (18), the term $-k_p(\hat{p}_{13}^2(t) - p_{13}^{*2}(t))$ is not shown in (24) but replaced by zero, because robot 2 does not have the knowledge of $p_{13}^{*2}(t)$. The relative velocity \dot{p}_{13}^2 required by robot 2 can be measured by using $\dot{p}_{13}^2 = \dot{p}_{12}^2 - \dot{p}_{32}^2$. Now, we are ready to present the main results.

Theorem 3: Under the simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws (24)-(27) and Assumptions 2, 3 and 4, the estimation errors $\tilde{p}_{e1i}^2(t) = \hat{p}_{1i}^2(t) - p_{1i}^2(t)$, $\tilde{p}_{e1i}^3(t) = \hat{p}_{1i}^3(t) - p_{1i}^3(t)$ and the formation errors $\tilde{p}_{f1i}^i(t)$, $i = 2, 3$ globally and exponentially converge to zero if and only if there exist positive scalars γ_5, γ_6, T_3 such that $\forall t > 0$,

$$\gamma_5 I_{12} \leq \int_t^{t+T_3} Q_1^\top(\tau) Q_1(\tau) d\tau \leq \gamma_6 I_{12}, \quad (28)$$

where $Q_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{k_c} M_2^{\Delta 123} & 0_{2 \times 2} & 0_{2 \times 2} \\ 0_{2 \times 2} & \sqrt{k_c} M_2^{\Delta 123} & 0_{2 \times 2} \\ \sqrt{k_p} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \sqrt{k_p} \begin{bmatrix} I_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \sqrt{k_p} I_4 \end{bmatrix}$. Moreover, if $\exists \tau_0 \in [t, t + T_3]$ for $\forall t > 0$ such that $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(\tau_0) \neq 0$, then (28) always holds under the simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws (24)-(27). \square

The proof of Theorem 3 is given in Appendix D. Although the matrix $Q_1^\top Q_1$ in the condition (28) is more complicated than the corresponding one in (21), the sufficient checking condition in Theorem 3 is the same as the corresponding one in Theorem 2, i.e., $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t)$ is not always zero. In addition, although we do not need to use the estimated relative position \hat{p}_{13}^2 in (25), we still need to design estimator \hat{p}_{13}^2 in (24) due to the reason mentioned in Remark 6.

Remark 9: When robots 2 and 3 have different and unknown oriented coordinate frames in Theorem 3, the desired formation's non-collinearity cannot be checked directly via the robots' available measurements and communication, but can be checked under the assistance of relative orientation estimation algorithms based on some environmental landmarks [33]. However, this is not the case for the scenario that robots 2 and 3 have aligned coordinate frames in Theorem 2 where the desired formation's non-collinearity can be checked easily via the communication link between robots 2 and 3, which is an advantage of (18)-(20) over (24)-(27).

Remark 10: Compared with (18)-(20), Theorem 3 requires that robot 1's velocity converges to zero exponentially, for which the information p_1^2 and p_1^3 are avoided in (25) and (27). Although \dot{p}_1 converges to zero, the desired formation is still time-varying since \dot{p}_{12}^{*2} and \dot{p}_{12}^{*3} are time-varying. In practice, robot 1 can also be replaced by a landmark (in this case $\dot{p}_1 = 0$) which can be commonly seen by the other robots.

IV. RELATIVE LOCALIZATION AND FORMATION CONTROL FOR N -ROBOT CASE

After investigating the 3-robot case, we now discuss the relative localization and formation for N -robot case ($N > 3$).

A. Construction of desired formations and their communication and measurement topology

Since persistent excitation conditions only hold for dynamic formations and an efficient way to achieve dynamic formations is via the leader-follower manner [25], [32], [37], we construct the desired formation in a directed and triangulated manner such that the constructed formation is uniquely determined and the relative localization among neighboring robots can be executed. To this end, we first define directed and triangulated formations.

Definition 1: Two robots i and j are said to be added into an existing formation in Class-I triangular addition if there is a robot k in the existing formation which forms $\triangle ijk$ with robots i, j by adding edges ik, jk . A robot i is said to be added into an existing formation in Class-II triangular addition if there are two robots j, k in the existing formation which forms $\triangle ijk$ with robot i by adding edges ij, ik .

Definition 2: An N -robot formation is said to be a directed and triangulated formation if it can be constructed starting from the leader robot 1 and adding the remaining robots sequentially through Class-I triangular addition or Class-II triangular addition. Moreover, the directed and triangulated formation is specified by the relative positions of the directed spanning tree whose root node is robot 1 and directed edges are constructed from the corresponding Class-I and Class-II triangular additions.

For example, the formation in Fig. 2 is constructed by starting from the leader robot 1, and adding robots 2 and 3 by $\triangle 123$ (Class I), then adding the robots 4, 5 by $\triangle 245$ (Class I), then adding the robots 6, 7 by $\triangle 367$ (Class I), then adding the robot 8 by $\triangle 568$ (Class II). Then, the desired formation is specified by the relative positions $p_{21}^*, p_{31}^*, p_{42}^*, p_{52}^*, p_{63}^*, p_{73}^*$, and p_{85}^*, p_{86}^* , under which the desired formation consisting of the 8 robots is uniquely determined.

Fig. 2. Construction of directed and triangulated formation

For the Class-I triangular addition in Definition 1, robots i and j are required to communicate with each other and measure their respective interior angles and derivatives of interior angles within $\triangle ijk$, and robot k does not need to communicate with anyone and measure anything. While for

the Class-II triangular addition in Definition 1, at least one of the robots j, k , say j , needs to communicate with robot i , and both of j and i need to measure their respective interior angles and derivatives of interior angles within \triangle_{ijk} , and robot k does not need to communicate with anyone and measure anything. Combining these communication and measurement sub-topology related with all triangular addition operations yields the overall communication and measurement topology.

B. Relative localization for N -robot case

Because of the structure of the directed and triangulated formation, we only need to consider Class-I and Class-II triangular additions. For both of the Class-I and Class-II triangular additions, the robots to be added need to execute the relative position estimator (15) using their available measurements and communication, under which the relative positions with respect to its two neighboring robots can be obtained according to Theorem 1. Therefore, it is straightforward to have the relative localization for N -robot case by constructing the formation in a directed and triangulated manner.

C. Simultaneous relative localization and formation control

According to the construction of the desired formation in Section IV. A, we also only need to consider Class-I and Class-II triangular additions for the N -robot simultaneous relative localization and formation control. For Class-I triangular addition, we have discussed the simultaneous relative localization and formation control within time-varying \triangle_{123} in Section III.C, which can be straightforwardly extended to the simultaneous relative localization and formation control for the other triangular sub-formations constructed by Class-I addition. For Class-II triangular addition, although we need two robots j and k in the existing formation to assist robot i 's relative localization, one desired relative position p_{ij}^* will be enough for robot i to achieve the desired time-varying triangular formation with respect to the neighboring robots j and k . Therefore, in this case we design the simultaneous relative localization and formation law for robot i as

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_{jk}^i \\ \dot{p}_{ji}^i \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_{jk}^i \\ \dot{p}_{ji}^i \end{bmatrix} - k_c \left(M_2^{\triangle_{jik}}(\alpha) \right)^\top M_2^{\triangle_{jik}}(\alpha) \begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_{jk}^i \\ \dot{p}_{ji}^i \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ k_c \left(M_2^{\triangle_{jik}}(\alpha) \right)^\top \begin{bmatrix} \sin \alpha_{jik} R^\top(\alpha_{kji}) \dot{p}_{ij}^i - \sin \alpha_{ikj} \dot{p}_{kj}^i \\ \sin \alpha_{kji} R^\top(\alpha_{ikj}) \dot{p}_{kj}^i - \sin \alpha_{jik} \dot{p}_{ki}^i \end{bmatrix} \\ &- k_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \hat{p}_{ji}^i - p_{ji}^{*i} \end{bmatrix}, \\ u_i^i &= \dot{p}_i^i = \dot{p}_j^i + \dot{p}_{ji}^{*i} - k_p (\hat{p}_{ji}^i - p_{ji}^{*i}), \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

where \dot{p}_j^i is obtained by communication for the case with aligned coordinate frames, but for the case with unaligned coordinate frames, we need to assume \dot{p}_{ij}^i and \dot{p}_{ji}^i being measurable such that \dot{p}_j^i can be known by using $\dot{p}_j^i = \dot{p}_i^i - \dot{p}_{ij}^i$. Indeed, this is a common requirement for controlling dynamic formations for robots with unaligned coordinate frames. In addition, the measurement of \dot{p}_i^i can be obtained from sensors such as optical flow or visual-inertial odometry [25].

Proposition 2: Under the simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws (29)-(30) and Assumptions 2, 3 and

4, the estimation errors $\tilde{p}_{ejk}^i(t) = \hat{p}_{jk}^i(t) - p_{jk}^i(t)$, $\tilde{p}_{eji}^i(t) = \hat{p}_{ji}^i(t) - p_{ji}^i(t)$ and the formation errors $\tilde{p}_{fji}^i(t)$, $i = 2, 3$ globally and exponentially converge to zero if and only if there exist positive scalars γ_7, γ_8, T_4 such that $\forall t > 0$,

$$\gamma_7 I_6 \leq \int_t^{t+T_4} Q_3(\tau) d\tau \leq \gamma_8 I_6, \quad (31)$$

where $Q_3 = \begin{bmatrix} k_c (M_2^{\triangle_{123}})^\top M_2^{\triangle_{123}} + k_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I_2 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0_{2 \times 2} \\ k_p I_2 \end{bmatrix} \\ \begin{bmatrix} 0_{2 \times 2} & k_p I_2 \end{bmatrix} & k_p I_2 \end{bmatrix}$. Moreover, if $\exists \tau_0 \in [t, t + T_3]$ for $\forall t > 0$ such that $\alpha_{ijk}(\tau_0) \neq 0$, then the condition (28) always holds under the simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws (29)-(30).

Proof 3: Using (29)-(30), the closed-loop dynamics can be written as $\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\tilde{p}}_{ejk}^i(t) \\ \dot{\tilde{p}}_{eji}^i(t) \\ \dot{\tilde{p}}_{fji}^i(t) \end{bmatrix} = -Q_3(t) \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{p}_{ejk}^i(t) \\ \tilde{p}_{eji}^i(t) \\ \tilde{p}_{fji}^i(t) \end{bmatrix}$ where $Q_3(t)$ is symmetric and positive semi-definite. Following Theorem 3 and its proof, it is straightforward to have the proof of Proposition 2.

Remark 11: In this section, the triangulated construction is used to achieve the multi-robot relative localization. The proposed relative localization approach is still effective when some redundant angle measurements are available. The reason of employing a directed topology is to achieve a leader-follower formation. Therefore, the proposed relative localization approach can be applied to multi-robot systems with a triangulated, fixed and undirected topology where inter-agent communication is allowed.

Remark 12: Compared with the existing works where interior angles or relative positions are directly controlled to achieve a desired formation [4], [6], [17], this work uses inter-robot angles and relative velocities to simultaneously achieve relative localization and formation control. The extra cost of this approach is the inter-robot communication, and the advantage is the existence of unique equilibrium of the closed-loop dynamics under the designed algorithms and given conditions.

V. DISCUSSION

In this section, we discuss the effect of noisy sensor measurements on relative localization and the collinear issue among neighboring robots.

A. Noisy sensor measurements

In practice, the sensor measurements are always subjected to noise, which usually has negative effect on system control and estimation. Indeed, (13) and (14) are nonlinear and coupled with three interior angles and time-derivatives of interior angles. Now, we discuss the scenarios where different types of noise exist separately. On the one hand, taking the direct calculation of inter-robot relative position (13) as an example, we assume that the relative velocity measurements \dot{p}_{21} and \dot{p}_{13} are subjected to additional noise $n_{21} \in \mathbb{R}^2, n_{13} \in \mathbb{R}^2$, respectively, whose magnitudes are small. Denote by $p_{13}^n \in \mathbb{R}^2, p_{21}^n \in \mathbb{R}^2$ the calculated relative positions from noisy relative velocities, noise-free angles and noise-free derivative of angles. According to (13), one has $\begin{bmatrix} p_{13}^n \\ p_{21}^n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} p_{13} \\ p_{21} \end{bmatrix} +$

$\tilde{n}_{123} = \begin{bmatrix} p_{13} \\ p_{21} \end{bmatrix} + (M_2^{\Delta 123})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} S_2 R^T (\alpha_1) n_{21} + n_{13} S_3 \\ S_1 R^T (\alpha_3) n_{13} - (n_{13} + n_{21}) S_2 \end{bmatrix}$. Then, the relative position error term \tilde{n}_{123} satisfies $\|\tilde{n}_{123}\| \leq \sqrt{2} \|(M_2^{\Delta 123})^{-1}\| (\|n_{21}\| + \|n_{13}\|) (2\|n_{13}\| + \|n_{21}\|)$. Since $\|n_{21}\|$ and $\|n_{13}\|$ have small magnitude and $\|(M_2^{\Delta 123})^{-1}\|$ is bounded by Assumption 3, $\|\tilde{n}_{123}\|$ also has a small magnitude, which implies that the negative effect of noisy relative velocity measurements on the relative position calculation is limited. In addition, by mathematical analysis, one can conclude that if the magnitude of angle noise is small, then the upper bound of the relative localization error is proportional to the magnitude of angle noises and the derivatives of angles.

On the other hand, if the angle measurements are noisy, then the derivatives of the angles have higher possibility of being zero at some instants, which will affect the direct calculation (13). Also, the sufficient condition $\exists \tau_0 \in [t, t+T], \dot{\alpha}_{312}(\tau_0) \neq 0, \forall t > 0$ in Theorems 1-3 will hold with a higher possibility. However, if the noise is random, then the derivatives of the angles and the norm of the matrix $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ may become unbounded. To deal with this issue, a low-pass filter (e.g., a moving average algorithm) is highly recommended to be embedded into the signal processing from the raw angle measurements to the angles used for the relative localization. It is worth mentioning that if the sum of the three interior angles' measurements does not equal π or 5π under the existence of noises, we can minimize this negative effect by employing the method in [21] to ensure that the condition (11) always holds.

B. Collinearity issue

As mentioned in Remark 5, a collinearity among three neighboring robots can violate Assumption 3 which is needed in Theorems 1-3. If three neighboring robots are initialized far away from the desired formation, e.g., $\alpha_{123}(0) \in (0, \pi), \alpha_{123}^* \in (\pi, 2\pi)$, then a collinearity cannot be avoided during the transition from the initial formation to the desired formation.

Note that if a collinearity occurs among three neighboring robots i, j and k , then two of the derivative of angles $\dot{\alpha}_{ijk}, \dot{\alpha}_{jki}, \dot{\alpha}_{kij}$ become infinite, which makes (13) invalid and (15),(18) not well-defined at this collinear instant. To deal with this issue, we can set $\dot{\alpha}_{ijk}$ as zero once α_{ijk} is detected to be zero. In this way, the estimations $\hat{p}_{12}, \hat{p}_{13}$ and control inputs u_2, u_3 in (18)-(20) will always be finite, even at collinear instants. For each such instant $t = t_1 > 0$,

the closed-loop dynamics (48) is reduced to
$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{p}}_{e13}(t) \\ \dot{\hat{p}}_{e12}(t) \\ \dot{\hat{p}}_{f13}(t) \\ \dot{\hat{p}}_{f12}(t) \end{bmatrix} = -k_p \begin{bmatrix} I_4 & I_4 \\ I_4 & I_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_{e13}(t) \\ \hat{p}_{e12}(t) \\ \hat{p}_{f13}(t) \\ \hat{p}_{f12}(t) \end{bmatrix}$$
 whose equilibrium set is $\{\hat{p}_{12}(t) = p_{12}^*(t), \hat{p}_{13}(t) = p_{13}^*(t)\}$. However, the desired relative positions $p_{12}^*(t), p_{13}^*(t)$ are time-varying and pre-defined, for which in general $\hat{p}_{12}(t_1) \neq p_{12}^*(t_1), \hat{p}_{13}(t_1) \neq p_{13}^*(t_1)$, and even when $\hat{p}_{12}(t_1) = p_{12}^*(t_1), \hat{p}_{13}(t_1) = p_{13}^*(t_1)$, one has $\hat{p}_{12}(t_1^+) \neq p_{12}^*(t_1^+), \hat{p}_{13}(t_1^+) \neq p_{13}^*(t_1^+)$. Since the collinear situation is not an equilibrium state of the dynamics (18)-(20), the robots can finally escape away from the collinear situation,

after which the combined formation error and estimation error will become smaller since $\dot{V}_1(t) \leq 0$ according to (53). In addition, due to the existence of noise and digital signal processing, the measured angle usually is not exactly zero. Therefore, when the angle α_{ijk} satisfies $|\text{Mod}(\alpha_{ijk}, 2\pi)| < \epsilon_0$ where ϵ_0 is a small positive constant, we can conclude that α_{ijk} is sufficiently close to zero or 2π . Moreover, since $\dot{V}_1(t) \leq 0$, the collinearity issue can also be avoided by constraining the initial formation error and initial estimation error to be sufficiently small. To obtain angle measurements at collinear scenarios, one needs to use a panoramic camera or directional sensor arrays.

C. Estimator design when derivatives of interior angles are unavailable

Usually, the derivatives of angles are noisy and difficult to be obtained directly from sensors. Instead, according to [5], one can design an estimator to obtain the derivatives of interior angles from the interior angle measurements. Taking α_{123} as an example, the estimator can be designed as [5], [14]

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\varphi}_1(t) &= \varphi_2(t), \\ \dot{\varphi}_2(t) &= -\eta^2 t^2 \varphi_2(t) - 2\eta t \varphi_1(t) + \eta^2 t^2 \alpha_{123}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where $\eta \in \mathbb{R}^+$. Since $\alpha_{123}(t)$ is bounded, according to [14, Thm 1], $\varphi_2(t)$ asymptotically converges to $\dot{\alpha}_{123}(t)$.

VI. SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTS

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed relative localization and formation control approach, we conduct a series of numerical examples and real experiments to validate the predicted results from the theory.

A. Relative localization among four robots

The numerical example in this subsection consider the harmonic circumnavigation mission for four robots where the leader robot will move along a circle, while follower robots will follow the leader robot and change their relative positions in a periodic and harmonic way. In this scenario, we consider that all the robots share a common coordinate frame.

In this case, given the leader robot 1, the structure of the four-robot system follows the triangulated construction method outlined in Section IV. Specifically, a Class-I triangular addition is first used to incorporate robots 2 and 3, followed by a Class-II triangular addition to incorporate robot 4. Then, the four robots move with assigned trajectories $p_1(t), p_2(t), p_3(t), p_4(t)$, respectively. The aim is to use the dynamical estimator (15) to achieve $\hat{p}_{13}(t) \rightarrow p_{13}(t), \hat{p}_{21}(t) \rightarrow p_{21}(t), \hat{p}_{42}(t) \rightarrow p_{42}(t), \hat{p}_{43}(t) \rightarrow p_{43}(t)$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Assign the trajectories $p_1(t), p_2(t), p_3(t), p_4(t)$ as $p_1(t) = 10 * [\cos 0.5t; \sin 0.5t], p_2(t) = (12 + \cos(10t)) * [\cos(0.5t - \pi/6); \sin(0.5t - \pi/6)], p_3(t) = (8 - \cos(10t)) * [\cos(0.5t - \pi/6); \sin(0.5t - \pi/6)], p_4(t) = 14 * [\cos(0.5t - \pi/3); \sin(0.5t - \pi/3)]$. which are shown in Fig. 3.

Under the given trajectories, it can be checked that $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t)$ periodically becomes zero, which is shown in Fig. 4. Therefore, when using the direct calculation approach (13) to obtain

Fig. 3. Moving trajectories of the four robots

 Fig. 4. Evolution of $\alpha_{312}(t)$

the relative positions, the calculation will be singular/invalid at these time instants when $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t) = 0$, which happen 24 times within $t \in [0s, 15s]$.

Instead of using the direct calculation approach, we employ the dynamical estimators (15) to estimate $p_{12}(t)$ and $p_{13}(t)$, where the gain is selected as $k_c = 2$. The estimation errors $\tilde{p}_{eij}(t) = \hat{p}_{ij}(t) - p_{ij}(t)$ are shown in Fig. 5. Although $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(t) = 0$ happens many times during $t \in [0s, 15s]$, the estimated relative positions are continuous and the estimation errors converge to zero within seconds. Although the maximum initial error reaches 7 m in Fig. 5, the results demonstrate an exponential convergence of the estimation errors.

 Fig. 5. Estimation errors $\tilde{p}_{eij}(t)$ under (15)

Fig. 6. Formation trajectories under (18)-(20) and (29)-(30)

B. Simultaneous relative localization and formation

In this case, we simulate the simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws (18)-(20) for robots 2-3 and (29)-(30) for robot 4. The desired formation trajectories are assigned as

$$\begin{aligned} p_1(t) &= p_1^*(t) = 10 * [\cos 2t; \sin 2t]; \\ p_2^*(t) &= (12 + \cos(20t)) * [\cos(2t - \pi/6); \sin(2t - \pi/6)]; \\ p_3^*(t) &= (8 - \cos(20t)) * [\cos(2t - \pi/6); \sin(2t - \pi/6)]; \\ p_4^*(t) &= 14 * [\cos(2t - \pi/3); \sin(2t - \pi/3)]. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

The gains are selected as $k_c = 2, k_p = 1$. The formation trajectories are shown in Fig. 6, the evolution of estimation errors is shown in Fig. 7, and the evolution of the formation errors is shown in Fig. 8, respectively. According to Figs. 6 and 8, although the maximum initial formation error is 7 m, the formation errors all converge to zero, and the desired harmonic formation pattern is achieved. Fig. 7 shows that all the estimation errors converge to zero in which the maximum initial estimation error is 14m.

 Fig. 7. Estimation errors \tilde{p}_{eij} under (18)-(20) and (29)-(30)

 Fig. 8. Formation errors \tilde{p}_{fij} under (18)-(20) and (29)-(30)

Additionally, as discussed after Theorem 2, the formation error $\|\tilde{p}_f\|$ and estimation error $\|\tilde{p}_e\|$ are bounded by $V_1(0)$ when the desired formation is static. To illustrate this, we consider a desired formation described by selecting $t = 0$ in (33). The evolution of formation and estimation errors is given in Figs. 9-10. Since $V_1(0) = 195.2$, the simulation results validate the claim.

 Fig. 9. Evolution of $\|\tilde{p}_{e1}(t)\|$ within $\Delta 123$

 Fig. 10. Evolution of $\|\tilde{p}_{f1}(t)\|$ within $\Delta 123$

C. Relative localization with noisy angle measurements

Different from Section VI. A, we consider that measurements $\alpha_{123}, \alpha_{231}, \alpha_{312}$ are subject to additional band-limited white noises with noises' variances 0.0001, 0.0003, 0.0002, and $\dot{\alpha}_{123}, \dot{\alpha}_{231}, \dot{\alpha}_{312}$ are subject to additional band-limited white noises with noises' variances 0.0001, 0.0003, 0.0002, respectively. The noise added to α_{231} is shown in Fig. 11. The corresponding relative localization errors are shown in Fig. 12, from which we can see that the proposed relative localization algorithms have robustness against angle measurement noise with small magnitude.

 Fig. 11. Noise added to the angle $\alpha_{231}(t)$.

Fig. 12. Estimation errors $p_{eij}(t)$ under (18)-(20) and (29)-(30) with noisy angle measurements.

Fig. 13. On the left-hand side, the three wheeled robots employed for the real experiments. On the right-hand side, a sketch depicting the system with the employed notation is provided. The green curve represents the non-straight motion of robot 2. The robots 1 and 3 give the information of their measured interior angles and the derivative of angles.

D. Experiments

The conducted experiment consists of three robots with two differential wheels and exclusive onboard sensing. In particular, in order to have the ground truth for the sake of comparison, the robots have a camera with $2\pi/3$ field of view providing images to detect ArUco markers [11] and a Raspberry Pi onboard. Each robot is tagged with a marker in front, as it is shown in Fig. 13. By knowing beforehand the size of the markers, the available algorithm in OpenCV [11] provides an estimate of the robot's relative position with respect to the markers. We employ such estimate as the ground truth. A video showing these experimental results and details is uploaded to <https://youtu.be/2PPLiSSVi60>.

The time derivative of the interior angles is measured indirectly. In particular, the interior angles are not measured with a constant frequency (see Fig. 14) because that depends on whether the markers are detected or not by the vision algorithm. Thus, we fit windows of five angle measurements to a straight line in order to estimate the velocity of the interior angles. Since robot 2 just moves forward or backward for a couple of seconds (see Fig. 14), such a methodology gives acceptable results whenever the velocity of the robot does not change its sign.

We show the results of the *direct* calculation resulting from applying Proposition 1 in Fig. 15. The results from our algorithm are compared with the measurements from the OpenCV's algorithm, which needs the marker's size beforehand, are quite similar. In fact, except for the random angle measurement noises, it seems there is a systematic discrepancy within the band of ± 25 centimeters. Since it is a

Fig. 14. On the left-hand side, the interior angles measured by the three robots. They are obtained from measuring relative directions as in Fig. 1. On the right-hand side, the relative velocity in X body axes for robot 2 with respect robots 1 and 3.

Fig. 15. Above, the red dots are the direct measurements of the x and y coordinates of p_{23} and p_{21} employing Theorem 1; the blue dots are the measurements obtained from the ArUco markers and OpenCV by knowing beforehand the size of the markers. Below, we depict the difference between the ArUco and Theorem 1 measurements.

systematic error, the bigger the triangle formed by the robots, the less significant it is, and vice-versa. These discrepancies are due to the sensitivity of our algorithm to the calibration of the velocity sensors. In particular, we recall that to apply Proposition 1, we need three velocities, namely, the relative velocity between the robots, the angular velocity of the robot (since the localization is based on a rotating coordinate frame attached to the robot), and the derivative of the interior angles whose sensitivity depends on the linear velocity and the size of the formed triangle among the robots. To compromise these factors, the max distance between robot 2 and the other static robots is about 1.6m, and the min distance is about 0.5m in this experiment.

We show the results of the estimations from applying Theorem 1 in Fig. 16, where we chose the initial conditions $\hat{p}_{12}(0) = \hat{p}_{23}(0) = 0$, and the gain $k_c = 5$. The selection of the gain k_c depends on the reliability of the calibration of the inertial sensors, i.e., on how much we give importance to the construction of M_2 in Theorem 1. A high value of k_c produces an *overcorrection* of the estimation. It can deviate substantially from the actual value as it happens with the direct measurements in Fig. 15. Overall, the estimate converges in a matter of a few seconds to the values measured by the OpenCV's algorithm and provides a *smoother* and *continuous* signal to be employed for other purposes such as formation control.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors thank Weiqiang Chen for his assistance on the paper's revision.

Fig. 16. Above, the red lines are the x and y coordinates of the estimations \hat{p}_{23} and \hat{p}_{21} by employing Theorem 2; the blue dots are the measurements obtained from the ArUco markers and OpenCV by knowing beforehand the size of the markers. Since we update \hat{p}_{23} and \hat{p}_{21} from inertial measurements, we can count on a *continuous* signal. Below, we depict the difference between the ArUco and Theorem 2 measurements, whenever the ArUco measurements are available.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper has proposed a multi-robot relative localization and formation control approach using angle measurements. Within a time-varying triangular formation, we have shown that two inter-robot relative positions can be directly calculated from the triangle's interior angles, derivatives of interior angles, and inter-robot relative velocities. Then, we have proposed a dynamical relative position estimator relying on the same three types of measurements. Further, we have designed simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws to achieve a desired triangular formation specified by the desired inter-robot relative positions. Moreover, the results for the three-robot case have been extended to the case with more than three robots. The key innovation of this work lies in the use of angle measurements for simultaneous relative localization and formation control, which eliminates the need for absolute position or relative position measurements. The proposed solution is scalable to large multi-robot systems with limited sensing capabilities and unaligned coordinate frames.

While this paper provides a framework for multi-robot localization and formation control, some aspects require further investigation. For instance, the discussions on the case with inconsistent coordinate systems deserve deeper exploration, in particular how agents can know their frames' orientation difference based on available measurements. Additionally, extending the proposed methods to three-dimensional scenarios and addressing challenges like robustness to dynamic communication topologies are promising directions for future research. These extensions will help in broadening the applicability of the proposed approach.

APPENDIX A: PROOF OF PROPOSITION 1

To evaluate when $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ is invertible, we need to check its determinant. To keep notations concise, $\sin \alpha_{123}, \sin \alpha_{231}, \sin \alpha_{312}$ are denoted as S_2, S_3, S_1 , and $\cos \alpha_{123}, \cos \alpha_{231}, \cos \alpha_{312}$ are denoted as C_2, C_3, C_1 , and $\alpha_{123}, \alpha_{231}, \alpha_{312}$ are denoted as $\alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_1$, respectively. According to the Schur complement theorem, one has

$$\text{Det} \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right) = \text{Det} \left(-C_2 C_3 \dot{\alpha}_2 \dot{\alpha}_3 I_2 - M_2^{(12)} M_2^{(21)} \right). \quad (34)$$

Then, we calculate

$$\begin{aligned} -M_2^{(12)} M_2^{(21)} &= \left[C_2 \dot{\alpha}_2 R^\top(\alpha_1) - S_2 \dot{\alpha}_1 R(\alpha_2 + \alpha_3 - \frac{\pi}{2}) \right] \\ &\times \left[C_2 \dot{\alpha}_2 I_2 - C_1 \dot{\alpha}_1 R^\top(\alpha_3) - S_1 \dot{\alpha}_3 R^\top(\alpha_3) R^\top(\frac{\pi}{2}) \right] \\ &= C_2^2 \dot{\alpha}_2^2 R^\top(\alpha_1) + C_2 C_1 \dot{\alpha}_1 \dot{\alpha}_2 R(\alpha_2) - C_2 S_1 \dot{\alpha}_2^2 R(\alpha_2 - \frac{\pi}{2}) \\ &- C_2 S_1 \dot{\alpha}_2 \dot{\alpha}_1 R(\alpha_2 - \frac{\pi}{2}) + C_2 S_2 \dot{\alpha}_2 \dot{\alpha}_1 R^\top(\alpha_1 + \frac{\pi}{2}) \\ &+ S_2 C_1 \dot{\alpha}_1^2 R(\alpha_2 - \frac{\pi}{2}) + S_2 S_1 \dot{\alpha}_2 \dot{\alpha}_1 R(\alpha_2) + S_2 S_1 \dot{\alpha}_1^2 R(\alpha_2), \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

where we used the facts (12) and $R^\top(\alpha_1) = -R(\alpha_2)R(\alpha_3)$. Substituting (35) into (34) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Det} \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right) &= \text{Det} \left[(S_2 S_1 R(\alpha_2) + S_2 C_1 R(\alpha_2 - \frac{\pi}{2})) \dot{\alpha}_1^2 \right. \\ &+ \left(C_2 C_3 I_2 + C_2 C_1 R(\alpha_2) - C_2 S_1 R(\alpha_2 - \frac{\pi}{2}) + S_2 S_1 R(\alpha_2) \right. \\ &+ \left. C_2 S_2 R^\top(\alpha_1 + \frac{\pi}{2}) \right) \dot{\alpha}_1 \dot{\alpha}_2 + C_2 (C_3 I_2 + C_2 R^\top(\alpha_1) \\ &\left. - S_1 R(\alpha_2 - \frac{\pi}{2})) \dot{\alpha}_2^2 \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

Using the facts $S_1 R(\alpha_2) + C_1 R(\alpha_2 - \frac{\pi}{2}) = R^\top(\alpha_3 - \frac{\pi}{2})$, $C_1 R(\alpha_2) + S_2 R^\top(\alpha_1 + \frac{\pi}{2}) = -C_3 I_2$, $S_2 R(\alpha_2) - C_2 R(\alpha_2 - \frac{\pi}{2}) = R(\frac{\pi}{2})$, $C_2 R^\top(\alpha_1) - S_1 R(\alpha_2 - \frac{\pi}{2}) = -C_3 I_2$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Det} \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right) &= \text{Det} \left[S_2 R^\top(\alpha_3 - \frac{\pi}{2}) \dot{\alpha}_1^2 + S_1 R(\frac{\pi}{2}) \dot{\alpha}_1 \dot{\alpha}_2 \right] \\ &= \text{Det} \left[R(\pi/2) (S_2 R^\top(\alpha_3) \dot{\alpha}_1^2 + S_1 \dot{\alpha}_1 \dot{\alpha}_2 I_2) \right] \\ &= \text{Det} \begin{bmatrix} S_2 C_3 \dot{\alpha}_1^2 + S_1 \dot{\alpha}_1 \dot{\alpha}_2 & S_2 S_3 \dot{\alpha}_1^2 \\ -S_2 S_3 \dot{\alpha}_1^2 & S_2 C_3 \dot{\alpha}_1^2 + S_1 \dot{\alpha}_1 \dot{\alpha}_2 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= (S_2 C_3 \dot{\alpha}_1^2 + S_1 \dot{\alpha}_1 \dot{\alpha}_2)^2 + (S_2 S_3 \dot{\alpha}_1^2)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

Note that when Assumption 3 holds, $S_i \neq 0, i = 1, 2, 3$. Therefore, letting $\text{Det} \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right) = 0$ yields $\dot{\alpha}_1 = 0$. It is also obvious that $\text{Det} \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right) \neq 0$ if $\dot{\alpha}_1 \neq 0$.

In addition, when $\dot{\alpha}_1 = 0$ and $\dot{\alpha}_2 = -\dot{\alpha}_3 \neq 0$, one has

$$M_2^{\Delta 123} = \dot{\alpha}_2 \begin{bmatrix} C_3 I_2 & -C_2 R^\top(\alpha_1) \\ -C_3 R(\alpha_1) & C_2 I_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (38)$$

where we used the fact $S_1 R^\top(\alpha_3 + \pi/2) + C_3 R(\alpha_1) = -C_2 I_2$. First, under Assumption 3, C_3 and C_2 will not be zero at the same time. Then, since an identity matrix is nonsingular, one has $\text{Rank} \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right) \geq 2$. On the other hand, it can be verified that every 3-by-3 sub-matrix of $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ is singular, which implies that $\text{Rank} \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right) < 3$. Thus, $\text{Rank} \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right) = 2$ in this case. Since Assumption 3 holds and $\dot{\alpha}_1 + \dot{\alpha}_2 + \dot{\alpha}_3 = 0$, the proof of the necessity part is straightforward.

APPENDIX B: PROOF OF THEOREM 1

According to (15), the dynamics of the estimation errors can be written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\tilde{p}}_{e13} \\ \dot{\tilde{p}}_{e21} \end{bmatrix} = -k_c (M_2^{\Delta 123})^\top M_2^{\Delta 123} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{p}_{e13} \\ \tilde{p}_{e21} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (39)$$

where we have used the fact (11). To prove the stability for (39), we firstly introduce a lemma on persistent excitation.

Lemma 3 ([1]): Let $W(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$ be regulated. Then, the dynamical system

$$\dot{x}(t) = -W(t)W^\top(t)x(t) \quad (40)$$

is globally and exponentially stable if and only if there exist positive scalars T_2, γ_1, γ_2 such that for $\forall t > 0$, $\gamma_1 I_{m \times m} \leq \int_t^{t+T_2} (W(\tau)W^\top(\tau)) d\tau \leq \gamma_2 I_{m \times m}$. \square

According to Assumption 3, one has that the estimator (15) is a continuous system, under which $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ is always regulated for $\forall t > 0$. Following the persistently excited condition in Lemma 3, one directly has the proof of the necessary and sufficient condition introduced in Theorem 1. Then, we prove the other sufficient condition given in Theorem 1 to guarantee (16), which is equivalent to showing that for any unit vector $y \in \mathbb{R}^4$,

$$\gamma_1 \leq \int_t^{t+T_1} y^\top \left(M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) y d\tau \leq \gamma_2. \quad (41)$$

Firstly, if $\exists \tau_0 \in [t, t + T_1]$ for $\forall t > 0$ such that $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(\tau_0) \neq 0$, then there also exists a small positive scalar ε_1 which is bounded away from zero such that $\forall \tau \in [t + \tau_0 - \varepsilon_1, t + \tau_0 + \varepsilon_1]$, $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(\tau) \neq 0$. According to Proposition 1, $y^\top \left(M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) y > 0$ when $\dot{\alpha}_{312} \neq 0$ and $y^\top \left(M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) y \geq 0$ when $\dot{\alpha}_{312} = 0$. Therefore, one has

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_t^{t+T_1} y^\top \left(M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) y d\tau \\ &= \int_t^{t+\tau_0-\varepsilon_1} y^\top \left(M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) y d\tau \\ &+ \int_{t+\tau_0-\varepsilon_1}^{t+\tau_0+\varepsilon_1} y^\top \left(M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) y d\tau \\ &+ \int_{t+\tau_0+\varepsilon_1}^{t+T_1} y^\top \left(M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) y d\tau \\ &\geq \int_{t+\tau_0-\varepsilon_1}^{t+\tau_0+\varepsilon_1} y^\top \left(M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) y d\tau = \gamma_1 > 0, \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

where we have used the fact that $M_2^{\Delta 123}(t)$ is nonsingular for $t \in [t + \tau_0 - \varepsilon_1, t + \tau_0 + \varepsilon_1]$.

Secondly, according to (11), one has

$$\begin{aligned} & y^\top \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123} y \\ &= \|M_2^{(12)} y_2 - \dot{\alpha}_3 \cos \alpha_{231} y_1\|^2 + \|M_2^{(21)} y_1 + \dot{\alpha}_2 \cos \alpha_{123} y_2\|^2 \\ &\leq 2[\|M_2^{(12)}\|^2 \|y_2\|^2 + \dot{\alpha}_3^2 \|y_1\|^2 + \|M_2^{(21)}\|^2 \|y_1\|^2 + \dot{\alpha}_2^2 \|y_2\|^2], \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

where $y = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \end{bmatrix}$, $y_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$, $i = 1, 2$ and we have used the fact that $\|a + b\|^2 \leq 2\|a\|^2 + 2\|b\|^2$ for vectors a and b with well-defined dimensions. Then, we calculate

$$\begin{aligned} \|M_2^{(12)}\| &\leq \|\dot{\alpha}_2 \cos \alpha_2 R^\top(\alpha_1)\| + \|\dot{\alpha}_1 \sin \alpha_2 R^\top(\alpha_1 + \frac{\pi}{2})\| \\ &\leq |\dot{\alpha}_2| + |\dot{\alpha}_1|. \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

Also, one has

$$\begin{aligned} \|M_2^{(21)}\| &\leq \|\dot{\alpha}_{123} \cos \alpha_{123} I_2\| + \|\dot{\alpha}_{312} \cos \alpha_{312} R^\top(\alpha_{231})\| \\ &+ \|\dot{\alpha}_{231} \sin \alpha_{312} R^\top(\alpha_{231} + \pi/2)\| \\ &\leq |\dot{\alpha}_{123}| + |\dot{\alpha}_{312}| + |\dot{\alpha}_{231}|. \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

Substituting (44)-(45) into (43) yields

$$y^\top \left(M_2^{\Delta 123} \right)^\top M_2^{\Delta 123} y \quad (46)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq 2((|\dot{\alpha}_2| + |\dot{\alpha}_1|)^2 + (\dot{\alpha}_2)^2) \|y_2\|^2 \\ &+ 2((\dot{\alpha}_3)^2 + (|\dot{\alpha}_{123}| + |\dot{\alpha}_{312}| + |\dot{\alpha}_{231}|)^2) \|y_1\|^2 \\ &= \gamma_2 < \infty, \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

where we have used the fact that $\dot{\alpha}_{jik}$, $j, i, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ are all bounded under the given condition in Theorem 1.

APPENDIX C: PROOF OF THEOREM 2

According to the definitions of $\tilde{p}_{e1i}(t)$ and $\tilde{p}_{f1i}(t)$, $i = 2, 3$, one has their dynamics from (18)-(20) as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\tilde{p}}_{e13}(t) \\ \dot{\tilde{p}}_{e12}(t) \\ \dot{\tilde{p}}_{f13}(t) \\ \dot{\tilde{p}}_{f12}(t) \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} k_c(M_2^{\Delta 123}(t))^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(t) + k_p I_4 & k_p I_4 \\ & k_p I_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{p}_{e13}(t) \\ \tilde{p}_{e12}(t) \\ \tilde{p}_{f13}(t) \\ \tilde{p}_{f12}(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (48)$$

where we have used the fact $\hat{p}_{12}(t) - p_{12}^*(t) = \tilde{p}_{e12}(t) + \tilde{p}_{f12}(t)$. Since (48) is a linear time-varying and continuous system, its stability depends on its system matrix. To use Lemma 3, we write the system matrix of (48) as

$$\begin{aligned} & - \begin{bmatrix} k_c(M_2^{\Delta 123})^\top M_2^{\Delta 123} + k_p I_4 & k_p I_4 \\ & k_p I_4 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= - \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{k_c}(M_2^{\Delta 123})^\top & \sqrt{k_p} I_4 \\ 0 & \sqrt{k_p} I_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{k_c}(M_2^{\Delta 123})^\top & \sqrt{k_p} I_4 \\ 0 & \sqrt{k_p} I_4 \end{bmatrix}^\top. \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

Then, according to Lemma 3, one has the necessary and sufficient condition (21) in Theorem 2.

Now, we discuss the sufficient condition provided in Theorem 2. To obtain (21), it is equivalent to showing that for any unit vector $\bar{y} \in \mathbb{R}^8$, one has

$$\gamma_3 \leq \int_t^{t+T_2} \bar{y}^\top \begin{bmatrix} k_c(M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau))^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(\tau) + k_p I_4 & k_p I_4 \\ & k_p I_4 \end{bmatrix} \bar{y} d\tau \leq \gamma_4. \quad (50)$$

Partitioning \bar{y} into $\bar{y} = [\bar{y}_1^\top, \bar{y}_2^\top]^\top$ where $\bar{y}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^4$, $\bar{y}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^4$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{y}^\top \begin{bmatrix} k_c(M_2^{\Delta 123})^\top M_2^{\Delta 123} + k_p I_4 & k_p I_4 \\ & k_p I_4 \end{bmatrix} \bar{y} \\ &= k_c \bar{y}_1^\top (M_2^{\Delta 123})^\top M_2^{\Delta 123} \bar{y}_1 + k_p \|\bar{y}_1 + \bar{y}_2\|^2 \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

Since \bar{y} can be an arbitrary unit vector, if $M_2^{\Delta 123}$ is not full rank, then one can always choose a nonzero \bar{y}_1 such that $M_2^{\Delta 123} \bar{y}_1 = 0$, after which one can choose $\bar{y}_2 = -\bar{y}_1$ such that $\bar{y}^\top \begin{bmatrix} k_c(M_2^{\Delta 123})^\top M_2^{\Delta 123} + k_p I_4 & k_p I_4 \\ & k_p I_4 \end{bmatrix} \bar{y} = 0$. On the other hand, if one chooses $\bar{y}_1 = 0$, then the lower bound $\gamma_3 = k_p$. Therefore, to guarantee the existence of lower bound γ_3 in (50), one only requires that $\exists \tau_0 \in [t, t + T_2]$ for $\forall t > 0$ such that $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(\tau_0) \neq 0$, under which the lower bound can be similarly guaranteed by following the proof of Theorem 1.

Now, we prove that the existence of upper bound γ_4 in (50) is naturally satisfied under the designed simultaneous relative localization and formation control laws (18)-(20). Note that Assumption 3 does not imply that the derivatives of the interior

angles are bounded, which, however, is needed to prove the existence of γ_4 . Design the Lyapunov function candidate as

$$V_1(t) = 0.5[\tilde{p}_{e1}^\top(t), \tilde{p}_{f1}^\top(t)] \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{p}_{e1}(t) \\ \tilde{p}_{f1}(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (52)$$

where $\tilde{p}_{e1}(t) = [\tilde{p}_{e13}^\top(t), \tilde{p}_{e12}^\top(t)]^\top$, $\tilde{p}_{f1}(t) = [\tilde{p}_{f13}^\top(t), \tilde{p}_{f12}^\top(t)]^\top$. Taking the time-derivative of $V_1(t)$ along (54) yields

$$\dot{V}_1(t) = -k_c \tilde{y}_1^\top (M_2^{\Delta 123}(t))^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}(t) \tilde{y}_1 - k_p \|\tilde{y}_1 + \tilde{y}_2\|^2 \leq 0, \quad (53)$$

which implies that $V_1(t)$ is nonincreasing. Therefore, $\tilde{p}_{e1}(t)$ and $\tilde{p}_{f1}(t)$ are bounded. Since $\tilde{p}_{ij}^*, \forall i, j \in \mathcal{V}$ are bounded according to Assumption 4, one has that $\dot{p}_i, i = 2, 3$ are also bounded. Using (43)-(45), one has that the existence of an upper bound of (50) is guaranteed.

APPENDIX D: PROOF OF THEOREM 3

According to the definitions of $\tilde{p}_{e1i}^2(t), \tilde{p}_{e1i}^3(t)$ and $\tilde{p}_{f1i}^i(t), i = 2, 3$, one has their dynamics from (24)-(27) as

$$\dot{X}(t) = -Q_2(t)X(t) - B_0, \quad (54)$$

where $B_0 = [0, 0, 0, 0, \dot{p}_1^2, \dot{p}_1^3]^\top$, $B_1 = \begin{bmatrix} I_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, $B_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I_2 \end{bmatrix}$, $Q_2 = \begin{bmatrix} k_c M_3^{\Delta 123} + k_p B_2 & 0_{4 \times 4} & k_p B_2 \\ 0_{4 \times 4} & k_c M_3^{\Delta 123} + k_p B_1 & k_p B_1 \\ k_p B_2 & k_p B_1 & k_p I_4 \end{bmatrix}$, $X = [\tilde{p}_{e12}^2, \tilde{p}_{e13}^2, \tilde{p}_{e12}^3, \tilde{p}_{e13}^3, \tilde{p}_{f12}^2, \tilde{p}_{f13}^2]^\top$, and $M_3^{\Delta 123} = (M_2^{\Delta 123})^\top M_2^{\Delta 123}$. Regarding the last part of (54) as an input, we first check the stability of the unforced system $\dot{X}(t) = Q_2(t)X(t)$. It can be verified that $Q_2 = Q_1^\top Q_1$. According to Lemma 3, (28) is the necessary and sufficient condition for the global convergence of the unforced system. As the inputs \dot{p}_1^2 and \dot{p}_1^3 converge to zero exponentially in the coordinate frames Σ_2 and Σ_3 , (28) is also the necessary and sufficient condition for the global convergence of (54) [19, Lemma 4.6].

Now, we discuss the sufficient condition provided in Theorem 3. To obtain (28), it is equivalent to showing that for any unit vector $\tilde{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{12}$, one has

$$\gamma_5 \leq \int_t^{t+T_3} \tilde{y}^\top Q_2(\tau) \tilde{y} d\tau \leq \gamma_6. \quad (55)$$

Partitioning \tilde{y} into $\tilde{y} = [\tilde{y}_1^\top, \tilde{y}_2^\top, \tilde{y}_3^\top, \tilde{y}_4^\top, \tilde{y}_5^\top, \tilde{y}_6^\top]^\top$ where $\tilde{y}_i \in \mathbb{R}^2, i = 1, \dots, 6$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y}^\top Q_2 \tilde{y} &= k_c [\tilde{y}_1^\top \quad \tilde{y}_2^\top] M_3^{\Delta 123} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{y}_1 \\ \tilde{y}_2 \end{bmatrix} + k_p \|\tilde{y}_2 + \tilde{y}_6\|^2 \\ &+ k_c [\tilde{y}_3^\top \quad \tilde{y}_4^\top] M_3^{\Delta 123} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{y}_3 \\ \tilde{y}_4 \end{bmatrix} + k_p \|\tilde{y}_3 + \tilde{y}_5\|^2 \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

From the reasoning after (51), if $\exists \tau_0 \in [t, t + T_3]$ for $\forall t > 0$ such that $\dot{\alpha}_{312}(\tau_0) \neq 0$, then $\tilde{y}^\top Q_2 \tilde{y}$ has a lower bound. Now, we prove the existence of upper bound γ_6 in (55). Design the Lyapunov function candidate as $V_2(t) = 0.5X^\top(t)X(t)$. Since $\tilde{y}^\top Q_2 \tilde{y}$ has a lower bound for any unit vector $\tilde{y}, \exists \gamma_7 > 0$ such

that $Q_2 > \gamma_7 I_{12}$, under which the time-derivative of $V_2(t)$ satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_2(t) &\leq -\gamma_7 X^\top(t)X(t) + \|X(t)\|(\|\dot{p}_1^2\| + \|\dot{p}_1^3\|) \\ &\leq -(\gamma_7 - \gamma_8)X^\top(t)X(t) + 0.25\gamma_8^{-1}(\|\dot{p}_1^2\| + \|\dot{p}_1^3\|)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

where $\gamma_8 > 0$ is an arbitrary positive constant. Thus, one can choose sufficiently small γ_8 such that $\gamma_7 > \gamma_8$. Since $\|\dot{p}_1^2\| + \|\dot{p}_1^3\|$ is upper bounded, it follows from (57) that $\|X(t)\|$ is bounded. Since $\dot{p}_{13}^*, \dot{p}_{12}^*$ are also bounded according to Assumption 4, one has that \dot{p}_2, \dot{p}_3 are bounded, which implies the existence of upper bound γ_6 in (55) according to (43)-(45).

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